

Semisimplicity conjecture for projective hypersurfaces associated to additive polynomials

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Abstract

We introduce projective hypersurfaces associated to additive polynomials over finite fields and show the semisimplicity conjecture for them.

1 Introduction

Let p be a prime number and q a power of p . The semisimplicity conjecture asserts that for any smooth projective scheme X over \mathbb{F}_q and $i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, the Frobenius correspondence acts semisimply on the i -th étale cohomology group $H^i(X \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$, where \mathbb{F} is an algebraic closure of \mathbb{F}_q and $\ell \neq p$ is a prime number (cf. [9, §4]). The semisimplicity conjecture is proved to be true for curves, abelian varieties and K3 surfaces (cf. [4, §1]).

Let $e, n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. For $1 \leq i \leq n$, let $R_i(x) := \sum_{j=0}^e a_j^{(i)} x^{pj} \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ be an additive polynomial with $a_e^{(i)} \neq 0$. We define $R := \{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$. Let X_R be the smooth projective hypersurface of degree $p^e + 1$ defined by the homogeneous equation

$$Y^{p^e} Z - YZ^{p^e} = \sum_{j=0}^e Z^{p^e - pj} \left(a_j^{(1)} X_1^{p^j + 1} + \dots + a_j^{(n)} X_n^{p^j + 1} \right) \quad (1.1)$$

in $\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1} = \text{Proj } \mathbb{F}_q[X_1, \dots, X_n, Y, Z]$. This hypersurface appears as a natural compactification of the Artin–Schreier variety X_R^0 defined by $y^{p^e} - y = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i R_i(x_i)$ in $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1} = \text{Spec } \mathbb{F}_q[x_1, \dots, x_n, y]$. Our main aim in this paper is to show that the semisimplicity conjecture holds for $X = X_R$. By the weak Lefschetz theorem, it suffices to consider the middle cohomology $H^n(X_R \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$.

Let $G_{\mathbb{F}_q}$ denote the Galois group of the extension \mathbb{F}/\mathbb{F}_q . Let $\text{Frob}_q \in G_{\mathbb{F}_q}$ be the geometric Frobenius automorphism defined by $\text{Frob}_q(x) = x^{q^{-1}}$ for $x \in \mathbb{F}$. We take a second root $q^{1/2} \in \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell$ of q . Precisely we show the following.

Theorem 1.1. *There exists a positive integer r such that $\text{Frob}_{q^r}^*$ acts on $H^n(X_R \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ as scalar multiplication by $q^{rn/2}$ for $i \geq 0$. In particular, the semisimplicity conjecture is true for X_R and all the eigenvalues of Frob_q^* on $H^n(X_R \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ are roots of unity times $q^{n/2}$.*

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Roughly we describe a strategy of its proof. Let $B_n := (X_R \setminus X_R^0)_{\text{red}}$. First we show that $H^n(X_R \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ is isomorphic to a direct sum $H_c^n(X_R^0 \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell) \oplus H^n(B_n \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ as $G_{\mathbb{F}_q^e}$ -representations. Frobenius semisimplicity on $H_c^n(X_R^0 \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ follows from the Künneth formula and theorems in [1] and [5], which say that X_R is a supersingular curve if $n = 1$. On the other hand, Frobenius semisimplicity on $H^n(B_n \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ follows from the analysis on the cohomology of certain varieties done in [7]. The cohomology $H^n(B_n \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ is described using the middle cohomology of the Fermat hypersurface S_n defined by the homogenous equation $x_1^{p^e+1} + \dots + x_n^{p^e+1} = 0$ in $\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n-1}$. The variety S_n has been studied in [6], [8] and [9].

The variety X_R has a large automorphism group and has interesting group-theoretic properties relating to Weil representations over finite fields (cf. [11]). In this paper, we focus on an arithmetic property of this variety.

Notation

Let X be a variety over \mathbb{F}_q . For an integer $i \geq 0$, let $H_c^i(X \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ denote the i -th ℓ -adic étale cohomology group of $X \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}$ with compact support (cf. [2] and [3]). We simply write $H_c^i(X)$ and $H^i(X)$ for $H_c^i(X \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ and $H^i(X \otimes_{\mathbb{F}_q} \mathbb{F}, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell)$ respectively. For a finite abelian group A , let $A^\vee := \text{Hom}_{\mathbb{Z}}(A, \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell^\times)$. We write $1_A \in A^\vee$ for the trivial character of A . For a finite-dimensional representation M of A over $\overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell$ and $\psi \in A^\vee$, let $M[\psi]$ denote the ψ -isotypic part of M . For a finite extension $\mathbb{F}_{p^r}/\mathbb{F}_{p^s}$, let $\text{Tr}_{p^r/p^s}: \mathbb{F}_{p^r} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_{p^s}$ denote the trace map.

2 Proof of Theorem 1.1

2.1 Analysis of open subscheme X_R^0

Definition 2.1. (1) A smooth projective algebraic curve C over \mathbb{F}_q is called *supersingular* if all the eigenvalues of Frob_q^* on $H^1(C)$ are roots of unity times $q^{1/2}$.

(2) Let X be a variety over \mathbb{F}_q . We say that X satisfies (F) if there exists $r \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ such that $\text{Frob}_{q^r}^*$ acts on $H_c^i(X)$ by scalar multiplication by $q^{ri/2}$.

If X is a smooth projective curve over \mathbb{F}_q , X is supersingular if and only if X satisfies (F) since Frob_q^* acts on $H^1(X)$ semisimply.

In the following, maps between cohomology groups are supposed to be homomorphisms as $G_{\mathbb{F}_q}$ -representations. For an algebraic curve C , let \overline{C} denote its smooth compactification. Let $r(x) = \sum_{i=0}^e a_i x^{p^i} \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ with a non-negative integer $e \geq 0$ and $a_e \neq 0$. Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ and let $C_{r,m}$ be the affine curve defined by $y^{p^m} - y = xr(x)$ in $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^2 = \text{Spec } \mathbb{F}_q[x, y]$. The following lemma will play a key role in a proof of Theorem 1.1.

Lemma 2.2. *Assume that $(p, e) \neq (2, 0)$. Then the curve $\overline{C}_{r,m}$ is supersingular.*

Proof. We may assume that $\mathbb{F}_{p^m} \subset \mathbb{F}_q$. We write C_r for $C_{r,m}$. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}^\times$. Let $K_\alpha \subset \mathbb{F}_{p^m}$ denote the kernel of $\mathbb{F}_{p^m} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p$; $y \mapsto \text{Tr}_{p^m/p}(\alpha y)$. The quotient $C_\alpha := C_r/K_\alpha$ is defined by $z^p - z = \alpha xr(x)$ and the quotient morphism $C_r \rightarrow C_\alpha$ is given by $(x, y) \mapsto (x, z) = (x, \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} (\alpha y)^{p^i})$. By [10, Lemma 3.28(3)],

$$H_c^1(C_r) \xrightarrow{\sim} H^1(\overline{C}_r), \quad H_c^1(C_\alpha) \xrightarrow{\sim} H^1(\overline{C}_\alpha). \quad (2.1)$$

Let ${}^0\psi \in \mathbb{F}_p^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_p}\}$ and $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^m}}\}$. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}^\times$ be the element satisfying $\psi(x) = {}^0\psi \circ \text{Tr}_{p^m/p}(\alpha x)$ for $x \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}$. Let $W_\psi := H_c^1(C_r)[\psi]$. Then $H_c^1(C_\alpha)[{}^0\psi] \xrightarrow{\sim} W_\psi$. The curve \overline{C}_α is supersingular by [5, Theorems (9.4) and (13.7)] (cf. [1, Proposition 8.5]). By this and the second isomorphism in (2.1), the eigenvalues of Frob_q^* on W_ψ are roots of unity times $q^{1/2}$. Hence the claim follows from $H_c^1(C_r) \simeq \bigoplus_{\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^m}}\}} W_\psi$ and the first isomorphism in (2.1). \square

Corollary 2.3. *The curves $C_{r,m}$ and $\overline{C}_{r,m}$ satisfy (F). In particular, $X_{\{r\}}$ satisfies (F).*

Proof. The curve $\overline{C}_{r,m}$ satisfies (F) by Lemma 2.2. The curve $C_{r,m}$ satisfies (F) by the first isomorphism in (2.1). The last claim follows from $X_{\{r\}} \simeq \overline{C}_{r,e}$. \square

From now, we assume that $e \geq 1$ and $n \geq 2$. For $1 \leq i \leq n$, let $R_i(x) = \sum_{j=0}^e a_j^{(i)} x^{q^j}$ with $a_e^{(i)} \neq 0$. Let $R = \{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$. Let X_R^0 denote the open subscheme of X_R defined by $Z \neq 0$. Let $y = Y/Z$ and $x_i = X_i/Z$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Then X_R^0 is defined by $y^{p^e} - y = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i R_i(x_i)$ in $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1}$. To show Theorem 1.1, we may replace \mathbb{F}_q by its finite extension. Hence we always assume that $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2e}} \subset \mathbb{F}_q$ until the end of this section.

Proposition 2.4. (1) *We have $H_c^i(X_R^0) = 0$ for $i \neq n, 2n$.*

(2) *The variety X_R^0 satisfies (F).*

Proof. We show (2). Let $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}$. We note that $H_c^j(C_{R_i,e})[\psi] = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $j \neq 1$. The Künneth formula implies that $H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi] \simeq \bigotimes_{i=1}^n H_c^1(C_{R_i,e})[\psi]$. Hence the claim follows from $H_c^n(X_R^0) = \bigoplus_{\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}} H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi]$ and Corollary 2.3. We can show (1) using the Künneth formula similarly. \square

2.2 Analysis of boundary B_n

We use the following elementary fact several times.

Lemma 2.5. *Let G be a finite group. Let V_1 and V_2 be finite-dimensional G -representations over an algebraically closed field of characteristic zero. We have a commutative diagram*

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 0 & \longrightarrow & V_1 & \xrightarrow{f_1} & V & \xrightarrow{f_2} & V_2 \longrightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow F_1 & & \downarrow F & & \downarrow F_2 \\ 0 & \longrightarrow & V_1 & \xrightarrow{f_1} & V & \xrightarrow{f_2} & V_2 \longrightarrow 0 \end{array}$$

as G -representations. Assume $\text{Hom}_G(V_1, V_2) = 0$. Then there exists a G -isomorphism $\Phi: V \xrightarrow{\sim} V_1 \oplus V_2$ such that $\Phi \circ F \circ \Phi^{-1} = F_1 \oplus F_2$.

We consider the equation (1.1). We take $b_i \in \mathbb{F}$ such that $b_i^{p^e+1} = a_e^{(i)}$. By replacing the homogenous coordinate X_i of X_R by $b_i X_i$ over $\mathbb{F}_q(b_1, \dots, b_n)$, we may assume that $a_e^{(i)} = 1$ for every $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Definition 2.6. (i) Let $B_n := (X_R \setminus X_R^0)_{\text{red}}$. This is defined by $Z = X_1^{p^e+1} + \dots + X_n^{p^e+1} = 0$ in $\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1}$.

(ii) Let $B_n^0 \subset B_n$ be the open subscheme defined by $Y \neq 0$. By $s_i := X_i/Y$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, B_n^0 is defined by $s_1^{p^e+1} + \dots + s_n^{p^e+1} = 0$ in $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n$.

(iii) Let S_n denote the Fermat hypersurface defined by the homogenous equation $y_1^{p^e+1} + \dots + y_n^{p^e+1} = 0$ in $\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n-1} = \text{Proj } \mathbb{F}_q[y_1, \dots, y_n]$. We define $Y_n := \mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n-1} \setminus S_n$.

We note that B_n is singular only at the point $[1 : 0 : \dots : 0]$. The complement

$$(B_n \setminus B_n^0)_{\text{red}} = \left\{ [X_1 : \dots : X_n : 0 : 0] \in \mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1} \mid X_1^{p^e+1} + \dots + X_n^{p^e+1} = 0 \right\}$$

is isomorphic to the Fermat hypersurface S_n by $[X_1 : \dots : X_n : 0 : 0] \mapsto [X_1 : \dots : X_n]$.

Let $U_n(p^e) := \{g \in \text{GL}_n(\mathbb{F}_{p^{2e}}) \mid g^\dagger g = I_n\}$, where $g^\dagger := (a_{j,i}^{p^e})$ for $g = (a_{i,j})$. Then $U_n(p^e) \ni g$ acts on B_n by $[(X_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} : Y : 0] \mapsto [g^{-1}(X_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} : Y : 0]$. Every scheme in Definition 2.6(ii), (iii) admits a natural action of $U_n(p^e)$. In the following lemma, all maps between cohomology groups are supposed to be homomorphisms as $U_n(p^e) \times G_{\mathbb{F}_q}$ -representations.

First we describe the cohomology of B_n^0 .

Lemma 2.7. (1) *We have $H_c^i(Y_n) = 0$ for $i \neq n-1, 2(n-1)$. The $U_n(p^e)$ -representation $H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)$ is irreducible of dimension $(p^{en} + (-1)^n p^e)/(p^e + 1)$.*

(2) *There exists an integer $r \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ such that $\text{Frob}_{q^r}^*$ acts on $H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)$ as scalar multiplication by $q^{r(n-2)/2}$.*

(3) *We have isomorphisms*

$$H_c^i(B_n^0) \simeq \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i \neq n-1, n, 2(n-1), \\ H_c^{n-1}(Y_n) & \text{if } i = n-1, \\ \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-(n-1)) & \text{if } i = 2(n-1), \end{cases}$$

$$H_c^n(B_n^0) \simeq \begin{cases} H_c^1(Y_2)(-1) \oplus \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-1) & \text{if } n = 2, \\ H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)(-1) & \text{if } n \geq 3. \end{cases}$$

Proof. The claims in (1) follow from [6, the proof of Theorem 1 and Theorem 3].

We show (2). Let $\pi: \mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^1$; $(s_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^n s_i^{p^e+1}$. Let U be the open subscheme of $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n$ defined by $\sum_{i=1}^n s_i^{p^e+1} \neq 0$. Let \mathcal{L}_ψ denote the smooth Artin–Schreier sheaf on $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^1 = \text{Spec } \mathbb{F}_q[s]$ defined by $y^{p^e} - y = s$ and $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\times \setminus \{1\}$. Let $\mathcal{L}'_\psi := \pi^* \mathcal{L}_\psi$. Let $U_1(p^e) \ni \xi$ act on $\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n$ by $(s_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mapsto (\xi s_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n}$. By [7, Lemma 3.7(2)],

$$H_c^n(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n, \mathcal{L}'_\psi)[1_{U_1(p^e)}] \simeq H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)(-1). \quad (2.2)$$

Let $R = \{R_i = x^{p^e} \mid 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. By $H_c^n(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n, \mathcal{L}'_\psi) \simeq H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi]$, the claim follows from Proposition 2.4(2).

We show (3). We simply write B^0 for B_n^0 . We note that $B^0 = (\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^n \setminus U)_{\text{red}}$ and $\mathcal{L}'_\psi|_{B^0} \simeq \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell$. Hence we have the long exact sequence

$$\dots \rightarrow H_c^i(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_\psi) \rightarrow H_c^i(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}}^n, \mathcal{L}'_\psi) \rightarrow H_c^i(B^0) \rightarrow \dots$$

We will show

$$H_c^i(B^0) \xrightarrow{\sim} H_c^{i+1}(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_\psi)[1_{U_1(p^e)}] \quad \text{for } i \neq n. \quad (2.3)$$

By [7, Corollary 4.6],

$$H_c^i(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_\psi)[1_{U_1(p^e)}] = H_c^i(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_\psi) \quad \text{for } i \neq n. \quad (2.4)$$

Assume that $i \neq n-1, n$. Then $H_c^i(B^0) \xrightarrow{\sim} H_c^{i+1}(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi})$ from the long exact sequence and $H_c^i(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}}^n, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi}) = 0$ for $i \neq n$. Thus (2.3) follows from (2.4).

Assume that $i = n-1$. We note that B^0 is denoted by Z in [7]. The isomorphism (2.3) is proved in [7, Lemma 4.7(1)].

We have $H_c^{i+1}(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi})[1_{U_1(p^e)}] \simeq H_c^i(Y_n)$ for any i by [7, Lemma 4.3]. This and (2.3) imply that $H_c^i(B^0) \simeq H_c^i(Y_n)$ for $i \neq n$. Thus the first claim follows from (1).

We show the latter claim. As in [7, the proof of Lemma 4.7(2)],

$$H_c^{n+1}(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi}) \simeq \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \geq 3, \\ \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_{\ell}(-1) & \text{if } n = 2. \end{cases}$$

By [7, Corollary 4.6 and (4.6)], we have $H_c^n(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{F}}^n, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi})[1_{U_1(p^e)}] \xrightarrow{\sim} \text{Ker}(\delta: H_c^n(B^0) \rightarrow H_c^{n+1}(U_{\mathbb{F}}, \mathcal{L}'_{\psi}))$. If $n \geq 3$, the claim follows from (2.2). Assume $n = 2$. The map δ is surjective. The $U_2(p^e)$ -representation $H^1(Y_2)$ is irreducible of dimension $p^e > 1$ by (1). Hence the latter claim follows from (2.2) and Lemma 2.5 with taking $V_1 = H_c^1(Y_2)(-1)$, $V = H_c^2(B^0)$, $V_2 = \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_{\ell}(-1)$, Frob_q^* as F, F_1, F_2 and $U_2(p^e)$ as G . \square

The following lemma will not be used.

Lemma 2.8. *The variety S_n satisfies (F). In particular, the semisimplicity conjecture is true for S_n .*

Proof. By the weak Lefschetz theorem, it suffices to consider only $H^{n-2}(S_n)$. We have a short exact sequence

$$0 \rightarrow H^{n-2}(\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n-1}) \simeq \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_{\ell} \left(-\frac{n}{2} + 1 \right) \rightarrow H^{n-2}(S_n) \rightarrow H_c^{n-1}(Y_n) \rightarrow 0$$

if n is even and an isomorphism $H^{n-2}(S_n) \xrightarrow{\sim} H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)$ if n is odd. If n is odd, the claim follows from Lemma 2.7(2). Assume that n is even. Since $H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)$ is an irreducible representation of degree > 1 as in Lemma 2.7(1), the claim follows from Lemma 2.5 and Lemma 2.7(2). \square

The abelian group $\mathbb{F}_{p^e} \ni \zeta$ acts on X_R by $[(X_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} : Y : Z] \mapsto [(X_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} : Y + \zeta Z : Z]$. Then \mathbb{F}_{p^e} acts on B_n trivially.

Lemma 2.9. (1) *For $i \neq n, 2n$, we have $H^i(X_R) \xrightarrow{\sim} H^i(B_n)$.*

(2) *Let $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^{\vee} \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}$. We have $H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi] \xrightarrow{\sim} H^n(X_R)[\psi]$ and $H^n(X_R)[1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}] \xrightarrow{\sim} H^n(B_n)$. In particular, we have $H^n(X_R) \simeq H_c^n(X_R^0) \oplus H^n(B_n)$.*

Proof. We simply write B for B_n . We consider the long exact sequence

$$\cdots \rightarrow H_c^i(X_R^0) \rightarrow H^i(X_R) \rightarrow H^i(B) \rightarrow \cdots$$

Let $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^{\vee} \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}$. Taking the ψ -isotypic parts and using $H^i(B)[\psi] = 0$ for $i \in \mathbb{Z}$, we see that $H_c^i(X_R^0)[\psi] \xrightarrow{\sim} H^i(X_R)[\psi]$. By Proposition 2.4(1),

$$H^i(X_R)[\psi] = 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq n. \tag{2.5}$$

We note that $H^i(B) = 0$ for $i \geq 2n - 1$ by $\dim B = n - 1$. Hence $H_c^{2n}(X_R^0) \xrightarrow{\sim} H^{2n}(X_R)$. For $i \neq 2n$, we have $H^i(X_R)[1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}] \xrightarrow{\sim} H^i(B)$ by $H_c^j(X_R^0)[1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}] = 0$ for $j \neq 2n$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} H^n(X_R) &= H^n(X_R)[1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}] \oplus \bigoplus_{\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}} H^n(X_R)[\psi] \\ &\simeq H^n(B) \oplus \bigoplus_{\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}} H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi] = H^n(B) \oplus H_c^n(X_R^0). \end{aligned}$$

Thus (2) follows. By (2.5), we have $H^i(B) \simeq H^i(X_R)[1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}] = H^i(X_R)$ for $i \neq n, 2n$. This implies (1). \square

We understand the cohomology of the boundary B_n .

Proposition 2.10. *Let $i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ such that $i \neq n$. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} H^i(B_n) &\simeq \begin{cases} \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{i}{2}) & \text{if } 0 \leq i < 2n \text{ is even,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \\ H^n(B_n) &\simeq H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)(-1) \oplus \begin{cases} \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{n}{2}) & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The former claim follows from Lemma 2.9(1) and the weak Lefschetz theorem for X_R .

We simply write B, B^0, S, Y for B_n, B_n^0, S_n, Y_n , respectively. We show the latter assertion. By $(B \setminus B^0)_{\text{red}} \simeq S$, we have the long exact sequence

$$\cdots \rightarrow H_c^i(B^0) \rightarrow H^i(B) \rightarrow H^i(S) \rightarrow \cdots$$

We prove that the coboundary map $\delta: H^{n-1}(S) \rightarrow H_c^n(B^0)$ is zero. If n is even, this is clear by $H^{n-1}(S) = 0$. Assume that n is odd. Since $H_c^n(B^0) \simeq H_c^{n-1}(Y)(-1)$ is an irreducible $U_n(p^e)$ -representation of degree > 1 by Lemma 2.7(1), (3) and $H^{n-1}(S) \simeq \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{n-1}{2})$, the map δ is zero.

Assume that n is odd. By $H^n(S) = 0$, we see that $H_c^n(B^0) \xrightarrow{\sim} H^n(B)$. This implies the assertion by Lemma 2.7(3). Assume that n is even. Since $H_c^{n+1}(B^0) = 0$ by Lemma 2.7(3), the sequence

$$0 \rightarrow H_c^n(B^0) \rightarrow H^n(B) \rightarrow H^n(S) \rightarrow 0$$

is exact. If $n = 2$, the assertion follows from $H^2(S) = 0$ and Lemma 2.7(3). Assume that $n \geq 4$. Since $H_c^n(B^0) \simeq H_c^{n-1}(Y)(-1)$ is an irreducible $U_n(p^e)$ -representation of degree > 1 and $H^n(S) \simeq \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{n}{2})$, the required assertion follows from Lemma 2.5. \square

Finally, we obtain the following on the cohomology of X_R .

Corollary 2.11. *Assume that $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2e}} \subset \mathbb{F}_q$. Let $i \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ such that $i \neq n$ and $0 \leq i \leq 2n$. Then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} H^i(X_R) &\simeq \begin{cases} \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{i}{2}) & \text{if } i \text{ is even,} \\ 0 & \text{if } i \text{ is odd,} \end{cases} \\ H^n(X_R) &\simeq H_c^n(X_R^0) \oplus H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)(-1) \oplus \begin{cases} \overline{\mathbb{Q}}_\ell(-\frac{n}{2}) & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

as $G_{\mathbb{F}_q}$ -representations.

Proof. The former claim is stated before. The latter claim follows from Lemma 2.9(2) and Proposition 2.10. \square

Proof of Theorem 1.1. All the claims follow from Proposition 2.4(2), Lemma 2.7(2) and Corollary 2.11. \square

Remark 2.12. (1) Let $\psi \in \mathbb{F}_{p^e}^\vee \setminus \{1_{\mathbb{F}_{p^e}}\}$. By $\dim H_c^1(C_{R,e})[\psi] = p^e$ and the Künneth formula, we have $\dim H_c^n(X_R^0)[\psi] = p^{en}$. By Lemma 2.7(1) and Corollary 2.11,

$$\dim H^n(X_R) = \frac{p^{e(n+2)} + (-1)^n p^e}{p^e + 1} + \frac{(-1)^n + 1}{2}.$$

(2) Let $H \subset \mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1}$ be a smooth projective hypersurface of degree d . It is well-known that the Euler–Poincaré characteristic of H equals

$$\frac{(1-d)^{n+2} - 1}{d} + n + 2.$$

The formula on $\dim H^n(X_R)$ in (1) is compatible with this formula with $d = p^e + 1$.

(3) The weak Lefschetz theorem implies an injective homomorphism $\iota: H^n(\mathbb{P}_{\mathbb{F}_q}^{n+1}) \hookrightarrow H^n(X_R)$. The cokernel of ι is isomorphic to $H_c^n(X_R^0) \oplus H_c^{n-1}(Y_n)(-1)$ by Corollary 2.11.

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